

Title: Thematic Summary: “No culture stops me from taking tablets”: Exploring community-level factors influencing pregnant women’s IPTp-SP uptake in Nigeria

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Study Context

This study explored the community-level factors influencing the uptake of intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy using sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (IPTp-SP) among pregnant women in two rural communities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Data were collected through focus group discussions (FGDs) with pregnant women and in-depth interviews (IDIs) with spouses, mothers-in-law, traditional birth attendants (TBAs), and community/religious leaders.

Theme 1: Descriptive Norms (Pregnant Women’s Views)

Behaviors typical in participants’ social or cultural context.

- **Traditional and Cultural Practices:**

Cultural norms did not restrict IPTp-SP use.

Example: “No culture stops me from taking tablets. Even if there is one, I will not follow it.” – FGD_Bayelsa Community 2

- **Ethnicity and Family History:**

Ethnic or family history generally did not discourage IPTp-SP use.

Example: “My ethnic tribe does not stop me from taking tablets during pregnancy... No history in my family/community prohibits pregnant women from taking prescribed tablets.” – FGD_Bayelsa Community 1

Theme 2: Injunctive Norms (Pregnant Women's Views)

Perceptions of what significant others approve or disapprove of.

- **Spouses:** Women inform partners but retain decision-making autonomy.
Example: “I will inform my husband about the drug prescribed... but he does not decide whether I use it.” – FGD_Bayelsa Community 1
- **Mothers-in-law:** Can influence decisions, sometimes discouraging use.
Example: “I won't take Fansidar if she tells me not to.” – FGD_Bayelsa Community 1
- **TBAs:** Offer advice on traditional practices but generally support medical treatment.
Example: “I can go to a TBA to be massaged, but she will not stop me from using Fansidar.” – FGD_Bayelsa Community 2
- **Community and Religious Leaders:** Limited influence; religious advice occasionally affects decisions.
Example: “If my pastor prays for me and tells me not to use Fansidar, I won't use it.” – FGD_Bayelsa Community 1
- **Friends, Parents, Siblings:** Social networks influence choices, but women prioritize personal judgment and parental guidance.
Example: “...if my parents tell me not to take Fansidar, I will not take it.” – FGD_Bayelsa Community 2

Theme 3: Injunctive Norms (Views of Significant Others)

Perspectives of spouses and TBAs on IPTp-SP uptake.

- **Financial Status:** Lack of funds may prevent access.
Example: “A lack of money can prevent my wife from taking the drug.” – Spouse
- **Traditions, Ethnicity, Religion, History:** Generally not restrictive; some spouses would relocate if traditions conflicted.
Example: “There is no tradition like that in my place. Even if there is, I will relocate my wife.” – Spouse
- **TBAs' Traditional Practices:** Encourage safe practices without discouraging prescribed treatment.
Example: “I tell the person with malaria to use bitter leaf to wash herself... but not to drink it.” – TBA

Summary

Pregnant women generally exercised autonomy in IPTp-SP uptake. Cultural, ethnic, and family influences were minimal. Mothers-in-law, spouses, religious leaders, and TBAs had varying influence, while financial constraints occasionally limited access.

Code	Definition	Example Quote	Source
<i>Descriptive norms (pregnant women's views)</i>	The prevalent behaviour in a typical situation		
Influence of traditional and cultural practice	Influence of traditional and cultural practices on IPTp-SP uptake	<i>No culture stops me from taking tablets. Even if there is one, I will not follow it</i>	FGD_Bayelsa Community 2
Influence of Ethnicity and Family History	Aspect of their ethnicities and family history influencing IPTp-SP uptake	<i>My ethnic tribe does not stop me from taking tablets during pregnancy... No history in my family/community prohibits pregnant women from taking prescribed tablets</i>	FGD_Bayelsa Community 1
<i>Injunctive norms (pregnant women's views)</i>	Perceptions of what others approve or disapprove		
Influence of Spouses	Influence of partners in encouraging or discouraging IPTp-SP use	<i>I will inform my husband about the drug prescribed when I get home but this does not mean that he will decide whether or not I am to use it</i>	FGD_Bayelsa Community 1
Influence of mothers-in-law	Ways in which mothers-in-law affect pregnant women's decision to take IPTp-SP	<i>I won't take Fansidar if she tells me not to take it</i>	FGD_Bayelsa Community 1
Influence of TBAs	Influence of TBAs on malaria prevention behaviours	<i>I can go to a TBA to be massaged, but she will not stop me from using Fansidar because I know that she does not know what a doctor knows</i>	FGD_Bayelsa Community 2
Influence of Community Leaders and Religious Leaders	Influence of community and religious leaders on malaria prevention behaviours	<i>My community leader cannot tell me what to take or not take. They don't know more than the HCPs who prescribed the drug in the first</i>	FGD_Bayelsa Community 1

		<p><i>place. I am not obligated to follow any community leader's instructions</i></p> <p><i>I believe in my pastor's prayer. If he prays for me and tells me not to use Fansidar, I won't use it</i></p>	FGD_Bayelsa Community 2
Influence of Friends, Parents, and Siblings	Influence of Friends, Parents, and Siblings on malaria prevention behaviours	<i>I know that people can be influenced by their friends, but none of my friends can stop me from taking a drug prescribed by my doctor...due to the respect I have for my parents, if they tell me not to take Fansidar, I will not take it</i>	FGD_Bayelsa Community 2
<i>Injunctive norms (views of significant others)</i>			
Influence of Financial Status	Influence of the availability of funds on IPTp-SP uptake	<i>With the way the country is, a lack of money can prevent my wife from taking the drug</i>	Spouse
Influence of Traditions, Ethnicity, Cultures, Religion, and History	Influence of Traditions, Ethnicity, Cultures, Religion, and History on IPTp-SP uptake	<i>There is no tradition like that in my place. Even if there are any, I will relocate my wife to another place</i>	Spouse
Influence of Traditions – views of TBAs	Influence of Traditions – views of TBAs on IPTp-SP uptake	<i>I tell the person with malaria to use bitter leaf to wash herself or pour oil on her body, but not to drink it, and remain in the sun for some time</i>	TBA